

Separation of Germanium from Arsenic by Paper Chromatography

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LEDERER¹ was able to separate germanium from Arsenic and other elements by paper chromatography using *n*-butanol saturated with N HCl using the ascending technique. The R_f values were Ge(IV), 0.26; As(V), 0.84; and As(III) 0.52. Ladenbauer and Hecht² made use of alcohols mixed with HNO₃ as solvents in the paper chromatographic separation of germanium by the descending technique.

In this communication we report our studies on the paper chromatographic separation of these two elements using ketones and ether solvent systems. Each solvent was studied in the three acid media—hydrochloric, hydrobromic and nitric acid.

Experimental

The descending technique was employed for the separations. Whatman No. 1 'Chromatographic quality' filter paper was used as the inert support. The strips were of the size 8 × 45 cm.

Chemicals and Reagents

Germanium dioxide sample was of the purest quality supplied by Fairmount Chemical Company, New York. The arsenious oxide and sodium arsenate were 'pro analyse' grade samples supplied by E. Merck.

The germanium solution (0.06%) was prepared by weighing the requisite quantity of germanium dioxide and mixing with 0.5 gm. of sodium carbonate and 25 ml of water. The sodium germanate thus obtained was neutralised with sufficient hydrochloric acid and diluted to 100 ml.

1% solutions of As(III) and As(V) were similarly prepared.

A 0.05% solution of phenyl fluorone in a mixture of ethyl alcohol and dilute sulphuric acid (75 : 25) was used as a spraying reagent for the identification of Ge(IV).

The yellow spot obtained when the paper strip was exposed to hydrogen sulphide identified As(III).

As(V) was identified by the benzidine-potassium iodide reagent spray which is prepared as follows : 0.1 gm. of benzidine and 0.1 gm. of potassium iodide were dissolved in 10 ml of 3 N HCl and the solution was filtered. The solution when sprayed identified the As(V) as a dark brown spot.

The solvents acetone, methyl ethyl ketone (MEK), methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) were of laboratory

reagent quality and purified freshly before use according to the standard procedures.

Results

The following Table summarises the R_f values with solvent systems of varying compositions :

Sl. No	Solvent system (vol. %)		R_f values			
			Ge (IV)	As (III)	As (V)	
1.	Acetone	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.95	0.72	0.85
2.	Acetone	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.80	0.12	0.65
3.	Acetone	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.68	0.50	0.86
4.	MEK	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.82	0.81	0.69
5.	MEK	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.16	0.12	0.42
6.	MEK	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.28	0.35	0.50
7.	MIBK	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.59	0.48	0.11
8.	MIBK*	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.10	0.10	0.13
9.	MIBK*	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.48	0.43	0.40
10.	Dioxane	(90%) + HCl	(10%)	0.74	0.70	0.91
11.	Dioxane	(90%) + HNO ₃	(10%)	0.40	0.83	0.73
12.	Dioxane	(90%) + HBr	(10%)	0.11	0.10	0

* Two layers formed and the upper layer was taken.

It can be seen that in all the cases the R_f values for Ge(IV) and As(III) are close, while the values for Ge(IV) and As(V) are wide enough to be amenable for separation. As(III) was therefore converted to As(V) by the addition of small quantities of hydrogen peroxide before running the chromatogram. This pretreatment gave very satisfactory separation of the two elements with the solvent systems 2, 5, 7, 10 and 11. Further, the separation time is of the order of 6-8 hours as compared to 22-24 hours with butanol-HCl/HNO₃ systems recommended by Lederer and Ladenbauer.

References

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β -Resorcyaldehyde as a Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ferric Ions

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WHILE a number of phenolic carbonyl compounds have been investigated as reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions, β -resorcyaldehyde has not been investigated so far for this purpose. The present article reports the use of β -resorcyaldehyde as reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of ferric ions.

Experimental

β -Resorcyaldehyde : 0.005 M solution was prepared in 40% ethyl alcohol.

NOTES

TABLE 1

DETERMINATION OF FERRIC IONS IN DRUGS BY COLORIMETRIC METHOD USING β -RESORCYLALDEHYDE AS REAGENT
 pH : 2.5 λ max. = 450 nm

Drugs	Manufacturing Company	Iron expected	Absorbance of ferric β -resorcyaldehyde complex	Iron calculated from absorbance
Polycytol tablet	Alembic Chemicals	Dried FeSO ₄ 0.195 g.	0.140	0.191 g.
Iberol tablet	Abbott Laboratories Private Ltd.	FeSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O 0.525 g.	0.210	0.523 g.
Miofer tablet	Napha National Pharmaceuticals	Ferrous gluconate 0.195 g.	0.105	0.194 g.
Ferfolindione tablet	'Indopharma' Pharmaceuticals	Ferrous fumarate 0.2 g.	0.130	0.198 g.
Iberol-liquid	Abbott Laboratories Private Ltd.	FeSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O 0.131 g.	0.105	0.130 g.
Tonoferon drops	East India Pharmaceutical Works	Colloidal iron hydroxide 50 mg.	0.100	47.9 mg.

Ferric Nitrate : 0.005 M solution was prepared by dissolving requisite amount in distilled water.

Sodium Perchlorate : 1 M solution was prepared in distilled water.

Procedure :

2 ml solution of ferric nitrate was taken in a beaker. 20 ml solution of β -resorcyaldehyde was added to it giving violet colour. 5 ml solution of sodium perchlorate was added to give an ionic strength of 0.1 M and pH of solution was adjusted by adding nitric acid. The final volume was made 50 ml. The solution was allowed to stand for 30 minutes. The absorbance was measured at different wavelengths using distilled water as blank.

Absorption Characteristics at Different pH :

The absorption characteristics of the complex in the pH range 1.0-3.0 showed that β -resorcyaldehyde gave a maximum colour at pH 2.5, stable for 24 hrs. The pH was adjusted with dil. nitric acid. The maximum absorption of light was shown by β -resorcyaldehyde complex in the region 420-460 nm. The depth of colour was not affected by the sequence of adding the reagent.

Composition of the Complex :

The composition of complex was studied by mole ratio method, method of continuous variation and slope ratio method. The formation of 1:1 complex was indicated and the stability constant was evaluated to be 3.786×10^8 .

Optimum Concentration Range and Obedance of Beer's Law :

The optimum concentration was 0.105 mg to 0.25 mg per 25 ml with β -resorcyaldehyde. Beer's Law was obeyed in the concentration range 1-56 ppm.

Effect of Diverse Ions :

It was found that 40 ppm of Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, or Ni²⁺ and

20 ppm of Mn²⁺, Al³⁺, Th⁴⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻ could be tolerated provided a limit of 3% change in absorbance was allowed. It was found that NO₂⁻, HCO₃⁻, I⁻, PO₄³⁻ and F⁻ interfered at all levels.

The suggested procedure was successfully applied to the analysis of pharmaceuticals containing iron in the form of colloidal iron hydroxide, ferrous gluconate, ferrous fumarate and ferrous sulphate. Liquid drugs containing ferrous sulphate or ferric hydroxide were diluted with distilled water and 2 ml con. HNO₃ was added. The mixture was heated for 10-15 minutes, cooled and diluted to one litre.

Tablets or capsules containing ferrous sulphate, ferrous fumarate or ferrous gluconate were treated with 10 ml con. HNO₃ and 2 ml HClO₄. The mixture was evaporated to dryness. The residue was diluted to one litre. 1 ml aliquot of diluted solution was used for measuring absorbance at pH 2.5. The results are given in Table 1.

Conclusion :

In phenolic aldehydes the substitution of H atom in position 4 by an OH group was most favourable as (the extinction coefficients of salicylaldehyde and β -resorcyaldehyde were 1125 and 2187) shown by the study of extinction coefficient of salicylaldehyde and β -resorcyaldehyde.

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